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COMPUTATIONAL METHODS FOR QUALITATIVE EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH: A HANDS-ON WORKSHOP

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1. *Interdisciplinary engineering education, linking different disciplines both inside and outside engineering, linking with society.*
2. *Niche & novel engineering education topics*

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a background paper used in the workshop ID 203. This workshop will discuss how computational methods can support the analysis of qualitative data in educational research and will provide a hands-on experience for participants to use these methods. Computation enables researchers to process large amounts of data and represent complex phenomena in the form of interactive visualizations and computer simulations. Most of the development of a subdiscipline on computational educational research has been focused on using learning analytics and educational data mining, which often require large data sets. However, we argue that computational methods can also be used for smaller-scale educational studies using qualitative inquiry. Existing computational methods can be used to gain insight from complex qualitative data, and to automatically categorize and group/cluster records from a dataset (e.g., student approaches to an open-ended task, teacher responses to an interview, documents), and to validate the outcomes from a research study. In this workshop, the research team will share different approaches to use these methods, with sample studies they have conducted over the last eight years, and a hands-on R programming activity to use these methods. The workshop participants will leave with curated machine learning and data visualization workflow tools that they can use in their own research.

1 MOTIVATION AND LEARNING OUTCOMES

This workshop provides participants with a hands-on experience on how computational methods can support the analysis of qualitative data in educational research and provides a hands-on experience for participants to use these methods. After the workshop, participants will be able to: (1) recognize the value of using computational methods to support their research endeavours; and (2) use machine learning algorithms and visualization tools to better understand educational phenomena.

2 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Computational science has become the third pillar of scientific discovery, along with the theoretical and experimental approaches. Computation enables researchers to process large amounts of data and represent complex phenomena in the form of interactive visualizations and computer simulations. Most of the development of a subdiscipline on computational educational research has been focused on using learning analytics and educational data mining, which often require large data sets. However, we argue that computational methods can also be used as supplements for smaller-scale educational studies using qualitative inquiry. Existing computational methods can be used to gain insight throughout the data analysis process including exploration, categorization, grouping and validation stages. In the exploration process, the researcher may use visualization techniques to identify patterns in the data. The researcher may also use automatic natural language processing techniques to assign qualitative categories to the dataset. The qualitative categories can be turned into numbers to use clustering techniques for uncovering groups. Finally, statistical tests such as the permutation tests require computational power, but allows to validate findings with statistical significance. For instance, Magana and colleagues [1] qualitatively analysed students' computational modelling process over a think-aloud protocol using content analysis. Fig. shows how the authors created a visualization using the counts from the content analysis process, to then use kmeans clustering to group students based on the similar types of knowledge they used over this process.

Fig. 1. Counts of content analysis to visualization to clustering

Similarly, Vieira and colleagues [2] analysed student written explanations of programming worked-examples to identify the different approaches students used to self-explain the example. They represented the resulting categories (columns) for each student (rows) in a heat map, and used hierarchical clustering with binary distance to group students with similar approaches (see Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Categories to visualization to clustering

Note that both examples used visualization and clustering techniques to analyse qualitative data with small sample sizes. However, each examples required of

different visualization and clustering techniques because of the nature of the data itself.

3 SESSION DESIGN

In this workshop, the research team will share different approaches to use these methods, with sample studies they have conducted over the last eight years, and a hands-on R programming activity to use these methods. The pedagogical foundation for the learning design of this study was guided by Cognitive Apprenticeship. Cognitive Apprenticeship [3][4] is a model that describes the components of learning environments that promote the development of cognitive and metacognitive skills. This model proposes the design of learning environments that merge “the content being taught, the pedagogical methods employed, the sequencing of learning activities, and the sociology of learning” [5] (p. 3). The implications for the learning design related to the organization of the sequence of instruction following the methods described on Table 1.

Table 1. Adaptation of cognitive apprenticeship methods for the pedagogical design.

Method	Definition (Collins et al., 1991)	Adaptation
0. Introduction (20 min)	The researchers introduced the different methods their uses to the participants. The participants are engaged in group discussion about how to analyse sample data sets. This step is not part of the cognitive apprenticeship model, but it is required for the workshop.	
Hands-on Activity (30 min): Workin in groups, the participants will use and modify sample implementations of the computational methods discussed in the introduction.		
1. Modeling	Consists of an expert’s performing a task so that the students can observe and learn from the process that are required to accomplish the task.	Providing an expert’s solution in the form of a worked-out example in an online interactive notebook.
2. Coaching	Comprises of providing opportunities to carry out the task and offering hints, reminders or feedback.	Allowing participants to use the expert’s computational model to solve a educational research phenomena introduced at the beginning.
3. Scaffolding	Includes providing supports to help the students to carry out the task.	Providing templates of code that provide the basic functionality coupled with in-code comments that guide the participants in implementing the critical functionality

4. Articulation	Involves engaging students to articulate their knowledge, reasoning, or problem-solving processes.	Asking participants to provide in-code comments to their own solutions where they will connect the disciplinary problem with a computational solution
5. Reflection	Encompasses enabling students to compare their own problem-solving processes with that of an expert.	Providing test cases so participants can validate their own computational solution.
6. Exploration	Involves eliciting students to engage in problem solving on their own.	Eliciting participants to adapt the new implemented computational model to solve a new problem.
Reflection (10 min): How can we use these methods for our own research?		

The workshop participants will leave with curated machine learning and data visualization workflow tools that they can use in their own research. For instance, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 depict a section of two different R Markdowns (i.e., websites with executable blocks of codes, that serve as interactive notebooks). Fig. 3 shows an example of visualizing patterns in a systematic literature review.

Fig. 3. Sample Code Block and Resulting Execution on <https://cvieiram.shinyapps.io/plotsLitReviewAPG>

Fig. 4 shows a scatter plots with sample data that is used to explain the kmeans clustering algorithm.

Question: Do you see any patterns in the plot?

Fig. 3. Sample Code Block and Resulting Execution on <https://cvieiram.shinyapps.io/unsupervisedAlgorithms/>

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WORKSHOPS

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